

Integrating Social Work into Healthcare: A Study of Workers' Perceptions, Attitudes, and Barriers in Obio Akpor Local Government Area

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Abstract

The present paper is on the perception and attitudes of health care workers towards integration of social work professionals in medical practices. Primary source of data was generated through self-administered questionnaires. The population of the study was 800 medical staffs, while the sample size of 267 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The study involved different cadres of hospital staff including; clinicians, nurses, radiologists, dental officers and hospital nutritionist. The research findings have shown that; the majority (54.6%) of the medical staff indicated that the hospital social workers' are not allowed to take decision effecting their work, thereby leading to a delay in decision making. The implication of this result is that social workers in the hospital will lack job satisfaction which may lead to poor service delivery. This portrays a prospect of social workers being underutilized. The general outcome of this realization is that most of the patients and clients would always fail to obtain care, assistance and advice from the social workers; hence be treated as normal medical cases. The study has determined that the perception of hospital health workers towards social work professionals is satisfactory as majority of the medical staff indicated that social work were a very important cadre in the hospital. Staffs who were not aware of the presence of social workers at the hospital recommended that they be employed; while those who were aware of the presence of social workers at the hospital recommended that their number should be increased and all medical staff be informed on the roles and functions of social workers in the hospital. It was recommended among others that Hospital social workers should fully participate in making ward rounds together with other health care teams in order for them to play their roles.

Introduction

Social workers have recently been posted to work in hospitals but their knowledge and skills are underutilized not intentionally but due to lack of in depth awareness on the roles and functions of social work professionals in medical service. The placement of social work professionals in medical service is of advantaged to patients being attended to in hospitals from the fact that not all patients require tablets and injections since the majority of patients suffer from social problems. Even those with debilitating medical conditions such as advanced HIV/AIDS, patients with cancer, severe heart conditions and many other cases are in need of social work professionals, (William, M. 2014). The National Association of Social Workers states the primary mission of social work profession which is to enhance human

well-being and help meet the basic needs of all people, with particular attention to the needs and empowerment of people who are vulnerable, oppressed and living in poverty. Social work in medical service is a new idea in many African countries including Nigeria (William, M. 2014). Social work in Nigeria is still at the infancy stage of its development. In recent years social work department has been attached with the Ministry of Social Welfare hence being called the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation. Some stake holders think that social work is not directly related to social welfare services and ministry of health. This is due to the fact that they are not fully aware of the roles and functions of social workers in solving patients' social problems in hospitals. The same applies to medical professionals, most of them are not aware of social workers' roles and functions in medical services. (William, M. 2014). The social work professionals have been integrated into medical practice but their roles and functions are not known by health care workers. At the same time health care staffs are not aware of cases which require social work professionals' interventions. The social work professionals are very much needed in patients care so that to play their roles but if their roles are not clear to health care workers this cadre will not be effectively utilized. Hence, this study seeks to investigate the challenges of integrating social work professionals into medical practice. A case study of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital

Research Aim and Objectives

Investigate the perception and attitudes of health care workers towards integration of social work professionals in medical practices.

Research Question.

What is the perception and attitudes of health care workers towards integration of social work professionals in medical practices?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

The study is designed to serve as a secondary source of data in social work research; this simply means the study is meant to aid researchers in carrying out their work. The medical

practitioners such as the physicians, nurses, psychiatrist seeking to develop their knowledge of the need of the roles social workers in medical setting can also find this study interesting.

The research is also being carried out in partial fulfillment of the requirement of a degree in Bachelor of Science in Social Work (BSW), this simply means that the research is equally helpful to the researcher.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings.

Another major limitation is that the respondent of this study are medical workers who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was greatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Social Worker

Within the United States, a social worker is an individual who possesses a baccalaureate or master's degree in social work from a school or program accredited by the Council on Social Work Education. Although all 50 states and the District of Columbia license or certify social workers, licensure and certification laws vary by state. Each social worker should be licensed or certified, as applicable and required, at the level appropriate to her or his scope of practice in the practitioner's jurisdiction(s).

Client

Client refers to the "individual, group, family, or community that seeks or is provided with professional services" (Barker, 2013, p. 73). For purposes of these standards, the term "client" refers to an individual. The term "patient" is more commonly used by social workers employed in health care settings.

Biopsychosocial–Spiritual Perspective

A biopsychosocial–spiritual perspective recognizes the importance of whole person care and takes into account a client's physical or medical condition; emotional or psychological state; socioeconomic, sociocultural, and sociopolitical status; and spiritual needs and concerns.

Bioethics

Bioethics is "the analysis and study of legal, moral, social, and ethical considerations involving the biological and medical sciences" (Barker, 2013).

Case Management

Case management is a collaborative process to plan, seek, advocate for, and monitor services, resources, and supports on behalf of a client. Case management enables a health care social worker to serve clients who may require the services of various health care providers and facilities, community-based organizations, social services agencies, and other programs.

Meaning social work

Social work is an academic discipline and profession that concerns itself with individuals, families, groups and communities in an effort to enhance social functioning and overall well-being (CASW2008). Social functioning is the way in which people perform their social roles, and the structural institutions that are provided to sustain them. Social work applies social sciences, such as sociology, psychology, political science, public health, community development, law, and economics, to engage with client systems, conduct assessments, and develop interventions to solve social and personal problems; and to bring about social change. Social work practice is often divided into micro-work, which involves working directly with individuals or small groups; and macro-work, which involves working with communities, and - within social policy fostering change on a larger scale (Francis J. 2005).

Research Aim and Objectives

- (i) Identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital

Research Questions

- (i) What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed at identifying challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical cadre. The identified challenges shall be communicated to the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Centre and the heads of department to make them understand the existing challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical practice. The results of this research study can help in developing strategies on how to eliminate those challenges hence maximize the benefits to clients who require social workers interventions.

This study will assist to create awareness to the local government authority on the need to strengthen the social welfare department in terms of allocating adequate funds as well as increasing the number of social workers into medical practice. Moreover, on job programs might be designed to orient all staff on the roles and functions of social workers into medical practice including cases required to be attended by social workers.

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One by-product of the psychiatric point of view in social case work is worth consideration in these days of overworked social workers, that is, the greater ease in work that it gives the social worker. The strain of dealing with unknown quantities is perhaps the greatest cause of fatigue in our work. . . . More exact knowledge of personalities with which we are dealing not only saves the worker worry and strain but also releases energy which can be applied to treatment. . . . Another result is that impatience is almost entirely eliminated. No time is wasted upon annoyance or indignation with the uncooperative housewife, the persistent liar, the repeatedly delinquent girl. . . . I know of social workers who looked with suspicion upon the careful preliminary study of personality, because they feared that the entire worker's interest might go into the analysis, and that treatment might be neglected. I believe that fear has been something of a bugaboo in social work. (p. 592)

The implication of Jarrett's address is that a focus on personality allows the social worker to get at the client's problem with ease, thus saving time for treatment. Another possible source of social work's attraction to psychoanalytic theory was Abraham

Flexner's 1915 address to the National Conference of Charities and Corrections, in which he said that social work was not a profession. Flexner defined professions as: (a) involving essentially intellectual operations, (b) having large individual responsibility, (c) deriving their raw material from science and learning, (d) working up their material to a practical and definite end, (e) possessing educationally communicable techniques, (f) tending to self-organization, and (g) becoming increasingly altruistic in motivation. He said that although social work had a professional spirit, it failed to meet all of the criteria for a profession because its members did not have a great deal of individual responsibility and lacked a written body of knowledge and educationally communicable techniques. Flexner's address had a profound effect on the field. Some social workers viewed medicine as a model profession and an intrapersonal approach as more professional than one focused on social and environmental factors. Nacman (1990) notes that, by the 1940s, psychosocial information was increasingly being used by medical social workers to make medical diagnoses and treatment plans. This was in contrast to its use, in Ida Cannon's words, "to remove those obstacles, either in the patient's surroundings or in his mental attitude, that interfere with successful treatment, thus freeing the patient to aid in his own recovery" (Cannon 1923.). The work of Helen Harris Perlman countered the tendency to use information primarily to make medical diagnoses and plans by emphasizing social science concepts over psychoanalytic ones and refocusing on society and environment. A focus on environment was reinforced in the 1950s by the community mental health and public health movements and the civil rights movement of the 1960s

Research Method

The Study Area

The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners.

Research Design

Nachimias (2003) defined research design as "the blue print that enables the investigators to come up with solutions to problems and guide him/her in the various stages of the research. This study adopts a descriptive cross sectional survey. Cross-sectional surveys are studies aimed at determining the frequency or level of a particular attribute in a defined population at a particular point in time. A cross sectional study is commonly used in medical and social science researches. A cross sectional study or prevalence study is the type of observational study that involves the analysis of data collected from a population or representative subset at one specific point in time. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services.

Population of the Study

According to Nachimias (2003) population is defined as “the aggregate of all cases that conform to some designated set of specification. Kombo and Tromp (2006) defined population as the largest group from which the sample is taken. The population of the study comprises all the medical staffs of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital working with social welfare department in the hospital which is about 800 in number. This number was obtained from the human resource department of the hospital.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Nachimias (2003) defined sample as “the sub set of a population”. Thus, in view of the fact that our study involves a finite population, a sample size that can be possibly reached is obtained. Kothari (2004) defined sampling techniques or procedure as “a definite plan for obtaining a sample for population given. The study sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamen’s 1970 formula.

The sample size was calculated by using the Taro Yamen Sample size determination formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Whereby; n=Sample size, N= total population (800) and e= an acceptable error (0.05).

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{800}{1+800(0.05)^2} = 266.7$$

In this research study the sample size was 267.

Data Collection Method

Questionnaire

The questionnaire involves a set of questions to collect information from subjects on their perceptions, feelings to the subject under study. It helps in providing accurate data that are quantifiable easily. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. Copies of questionnaire would be personally administered, followed up and retrieved.

Data Analysis Approach

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that “thematic analysis is a qualitative analytic method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns within data. Thematic analysis minimally organizes and described data set in details. However, it goes further than this and interprets various aspect of the research topic. Data collected from the field were structured to ensure consistency of responses. Data generated were arranged and coded according to themes and then fed into the data editor section of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0). Analysis were undertaken in two phases beginning with the demographic profile, using percentages, describes the frequencies of responses to various sample characteristics.

Secondly the research questions and findings were analyzed through mean scores and standard deviations

Validity of the Instrument

According to Babbie (2007), the term validity refers to the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. Validity is defined as the ability of the scale to measure what it is designed or purported to measure. For validity of the measurement to be established, there should be a complete absence of measurement error. It is important that a reliability and validity test be carried out comprehensively at every stage of the research work. Babbie (2007) posit that, after operationalizing, defining variables and applying different scaling techniques, it is pertinent to ensure that each research instrument employed be adequately tested for reliability and validity. In this study, the researcher ensured that the measure for reliability included an adequate and effective representative set of items that tap the concept. Serious effort was made to ensure that the scale items represented the domain or universe of the concept being measured. In other words, the measurement is a function of how well the dimensions and indicators of the various concepts are been delineated, which logically reflected the study variables. The validation of the instrument would be ensured through my supervisors vetting. Through this process, errors in the questionnaire such as ambiguity, contradictory questions, poor wording of questions, misleading or poor instructions among others would be detected and eliminated.

Tests of Reliability of Instrument

Reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to achieve consistent results each time it is adopted. However, Nunnally (1979) asserts that the reliability alpha values in determining the internal consistency of the instrument should maintain a minimum threshold of 0.7. Based on this, the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method was utilized in this study since it is the most predominant method of testing reliability in social sciences research (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson 2010).

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

Table 1 Work Experience of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
less than 5	100	48.8	48.8	48.8
5-10	29	14.1	14.1	62.9
11-15	27	13.2	13.2	76.1
16-20	32	15.6	15.6	91.7
21 above	17	8.3	8.3	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

Figure 2: bar chart showing years of service of respondents

From the data in table 2, 100 respondents representing 48.8 percent indicated that they had worked in the hospital for less than 5 years, while 29 respondents that is 14.1 percent had worked for between 5-10 years. Furthermore, 27 respondents representing 13.2 percent had been in the hospital for between 11-15 years, 32 respondent representing 15.3 percent had been in the hospital between 16 – 20 years, and 17 respondent representing 8.3 percent had been in the hospital for 21 years and above.

Table 3 Job Title Distribution of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Doc.	98	47.8	47.8	47.8
Nurs.	72	35.1	35.1	82.9
Valid OdaMedWrks	35	17.1	17.1	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

Figure 2: bar chart showing job title distribution of respondents

From the data in table 2, 97 respondents that are 47.3 percent indicated that they were doctors while 74 respondents that are 36.1 percent were nurses .Furthermore, 34 respondents representing 16.6 are other medical staffs working with the social worker in the hospital. Arising from this therefore, is that most of our respondents are in the medical doctor cadre.

Analysis of Research Question

Research Question

What is the perception and attitudes of health care workers towards integration of social work professionals in medical practices?

Table 3 Response Rates on Perception and Attitudes of Health Care Workers Towards Integration Of Social Work Professionals in The Hospital.

	Perception and attitudes of health care workers towards integration of social work professionals	SA	A	U	D	SD	Me an	Std.
1	I understand that social workers are part of the medical team and provide support for the well-being of patients in the hospital	113	66	6	9	11	4.27	1.08172
2	I have good working relationship with social workers in the hospital	81	91	9	11	13	4.05	1.10793
3	I relate with social workers in the treatment of	77	112	3	8	5	4.	0.8

	patients in the hospital.						21	5170
4	Social workers in the hospital are assessable therefore it is easier to refer cases to them	77	90	8	14	16	3.97	1.18148
5	Social workers in the hospital maintains there professional ethics, making it easier to confide in them	81	83	10	24	7	4.01	1.10698

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

The result of table 3 reveals that all items (1-5) have mean scores above 2.50. The statement ‘I understand that social workers are part of the medical team and provide support for the well-being of patients in the hospital’ has the highest mean score (M=4.27; SD=1.08172) followed by ‘I relate with social workers in the treatment of patients in the hospital’ (M=4.21; SD= 0.85170), ‘I have good working relationship with social workers in the hospital’ (M=4.05;SD=1.10793), ‘Social workers in the hospital maintains there professional ethics, making it easier to confide in them’ (M=4.01;SD=1.10698), ‘Social workers in the hospital are assessable therefore it is easier to refer cases to them’ (M=3.97;SD=1.18148). These show that all the items indicate that medical staffs have good perception and attitudes towards the integration of social work professionals into the medical institution. This is true since the mean values are above the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the agree range of the scale. Thus it is clear that medical staffs see social workers as team members in the hospital, have good working relationship with them, relates well with them because they are assessable and maintains their professional ethics in the hospital.

Discussion of findings

The research findings have shown that; the majority (54.6%) of the medical staff indicated that the hospital social workers’ are not allowed to take decision effecting their work, thereby leading to a delay in decision making. The implication of this result is that social workers in the hospital will lack job satisfaction which may lead to poor service delivery. This portrays a prospect of social workers being underutilized. The general outcome of this realization is that most of the patients and clients would always fail to obtain care, assistance and advice from the social workers; hence be treated as normal medical cases. The study has determined that the perception of hospital health workers towards social work professionals is satisfactory as majority of the medical staff indicated that social work were a very important cadre in the hospital. Staffs who were not aware of the presence of social workers at the hospital recommended that they be employed; while those who were aware of the presence of social workers at the hospital recommended that their number should be increased and all medical staff be informed on the roles and functions of social workers in the hospital.

Recommendations

- i. Hospital social workers should fully participate in making ward rounds together with other health care teams in order for them to play their roles.
- ii. Hospital staff should be educated on identifying cases requiring social work intervention. This would hasten referral of the patients as most patients requiring social work intervention are not attended.
- iii. Social workers should attend general clinical meetings together with other health care workers in order to maintain good working atmosphere and exchange experiences.

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